

3 books + 1

Tapuya: Latin American Science, Technology and Society

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Jungle laboratories: Mexican peasants, national projects, and the making of the pill, by Gabriel Soto Laveaga, Durham, NC, Duke University Press, 2009, 352 pp., \$104.95 (hardback), 28.95 (paperback) ISBN: 978-0-8223-4605-0, Cloth ISBN: 978-0-8223-4587-9
The experiential Caribbean: creating knowledge and healing in the early modern Atlantic, by Pablo F. Gómez, Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2017, 314 pp., \$29.95 (paperback), ISBN: 978-1-4696-3087-8, \$90.00 (hardcover), ISBN: 978-1-4696-3086-1, \$19.99 (eBook) ISBN: 978-1-4696-3088-5
Fascist pigs: technoscientific organisms and the history of fascism, by Tiago Saraiva, 2018, Print, Cambridge, MA, MIT Press, 344 pp., \$50.00 (hardcover), ISBN 9780262035033; \$19.95 (paperback), ISBN: 9780262536158
El Instituto Médico Nacional: La política de las plantas y los laboratorios a fines del siglo XIX, by Nina Hinke and Laura Cházaro, México, DF, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados, 2012, 228 pp., \$19.00 (paperback), ISBN: 978-607-02-2603-8

Three books. Three historical periods that span from the early modern Caribbean (namely, the incommensurable space of the Atlantic) to twentieth-century Europe, Africa, and North America; a category that – as we have learned in school – includes Mexico. Uncountable geographies that allow readers to travel in time and space, connecting ten years of work of three remarkable authors from a new generation of historians of science teaching in American universities: Gabriela Soto Laveaga, since 2016 Professor of History of Science, and Antonio Madero, Professor for the Study of Mexico at Harvard University; the Colombian physician Pablo Gómez, Associate Professor of History and the History of Medicine at the University of Wisconsin-Madison; and the Portuguese researcher Tiago Saraiva, Associate Professor of History and the History of Medicine at Drexel University in Philadelphia. Three books dealing with plants and animals as both techno-scientific human organisms and matters of exchange (Cook [2008](#)).

But, finally, there is also a fourth book written in Spanish and published in 2012 in Mexico City: left unfinished by the Mexican historian of science Nina Hinke, it was posthumously edited by her colleague Laura Cházaro García from CINVESTAV.

I met Nina Hinke in August 1997 in a Summer Academy held at the Max Planck Institute for the History of Science, which in the following years became a meeting place, a kind of invisible thread that can be used to follow the itineraries of the historians mentioned in this review. This is not to say that it was there that they/we had learned what to do, but the truth is that the MPI acted as a real and virtual space of encounter for those who wanted to experiment with other narratives. Saraiva's pigs, for instance, are descendants of Hans-Jörg Rheinberger's experimental systems (Rheinberger [1998](#)).

Nina Hinke (d. in 2004) studied in Mexico, Paris, and London. By the late 1990s, she had moved to study the practices that shaped scientific institutions and endeavors. In her book, she analyzed the National Medical Institute, one of the most relevant Mexican research and experimentation centers of the late nineteenth century, in charge of the analysis of plants and of creating national therapeutics. Nina rooted these practices in the expertise developed in colonial times which turned nature into a scientific and commercial object, or as Harold Cook (2008) would say, as a “matter of exchange.” Since then, the plants, animals, and minerals from the Americas have been the subject of several transactions and enterprises. With the establishment of the Institute in 1889, the plants were nationalized: the basis for the development of a national pharmacology. Plants were transformed into drugs and their chemical components, revealed by combining the expertise of field collectors, laboratory experimenters, and of those who observed their patients in the hospitals. Nina showed how those practices mobilized, connected, and recombined spaces, people, and historical traditions, keys to a framework where identities exist as historic events. These contingencies allow, as Saraiva’s book describes, the celebration of the Andean potato as a crucial element of the German soul. Or, as Hinke showed, a repertoire of Mexican *materia medica* done thanks to the fieldwork of American collectors, who botanized in Northern Mexico and sold and/or exchanged their specimens to the Institute’s physicians.

These arguments are also present in Soto Laveaga’s *Jungle Laboratories* – 2010 Robert K. Merton Award winner which contains stories about the search for wild yam called *barbasco*, a plant from the genus *Dioscorea*, which in the late 1940s replaced *cabeza de negro*, *cocolmea*, or *Dioscorea mexicana* as the ideal raw material for making synthetic steroids. The byproducts of this indigenous plant from Mexico altered modern medicine and “granted millions of women some control over reproduction” (2). From 1940 to the mid-1970s, *barbasco* was the ideal source of material for the global production of synthetic hormones. As a matter of fact, mass production of progesterone, cortisone, and oral contra-conceptives was possible thanks to the availability of these Mexican yams. By 1960 – says Soto Laveaga – more than 2 million women in the United States were using the Pill, and more than 100,000 Mexican peasants were gathering *barbasco*, a plant which today – despite the sheer number of individuals and the amount of expertise involved in the trade – is almost forgotten: by 1975, president Echeverría attempted to nationalize this industry, which would be eclipsed only 15 years later, due to the emerging industry of soy phytosterols exactly when the root was becoming depleted in the wild. *Jungle laboratories* is a subtle and nuanced account of how a wild thing acquires financial value and transforms the lives and economy of a local population, and the holders of the knowledge about how to treat the plant, and the expertise they used to negotiate with the representatives of the pharmaceutical companies.

There is no better abstract of *Fascist Pigs* than the one found in Saraiva’s university webpage:

I researched emblematic themes of fascist ideology, such as ‘rootedness in the soil’ and *Lebensraum*, by looking at the cultivated plants and domestic animals that materialized these ideas in the landscape in Italy, Germany and Portugal, and their respective imperial territories in Eastern Europe and Africa. The book connects geneticists’ research and food policies of three different fascist regimes, and it aspires to make laboratory production of industrialized organisms a central component of the history of fascism. (<https://drexel.edu/coas/faculty-research/faculty-directory/TiagoSaraiva/>)

On the one hand, wheat (domesticated in South Turkey), pigs (domesticated from the Eurasian wild boar *Sus scrofa*), and potatoes (domesticated in the Andes) were the

protagonists of the Neolithic revolution, but also of the continental breeding and chemical experiments of mid-twentieth century European fascist regimes and their attempts to achieve “food independence.” On the other hand, coffee, rubber, cotton, and sheep became the state artifacts in Kant’s vocabulary, (“technoscientific organisms” in Saraiva’s words) that “invaded” the territories colonized abroad.

In this book, no one would utter the words “Better a pig than a fascist,” the famous lines of Hayao Miyazaki’s *Porco Rosso*: even potatoes – turned immune to disease thanks to the development in Berlin of new variants resistant to warts, beetles, viruses, and late blight fungus – were recruited to serve as messengers of the *Führer*. In that frame, the research at the *Biologische Reichsanstalt für Land- und Forstwirtschaft* (BRA) – the Berliner Institute for agricultural sciences – is part of

the larger story of the expansion of the Nazi infrastructure through the German territory, of trying to establish stronger ties between the population and the national soil, and of guaranteeing the “nutritional freedom,” of the *Volk* and thus its biological survival. (99)

Pablo Gómez’s *Experiential Caribbean* reveals “the Black geographies of healing” in the seventeenth century, a space of interaction of the most diverse epistemologies and actors. Let us take the inventory of the therapeutical arsenal of a certain black healer, Diego López, who in 1640 included “several unspecified medical preparations coming from pharmacies in Cartagena, ingredients of which included tree branches and leaves, grains, and even an (Andean) emerald” (76). Diego also used “liquid of the Indies” that he bought from Portuguese merchants. His networks for the provision of medicinal tools were not only broad: they speak of the analytical difficulties of labeling healing practices and rituals in such an interconnected region. Healers – not only in the Caribbean, I would add – were omnivorous consumers of healing techniques of all origins, including the reading of books about the secrets of nature published and translated in Spain. They were literate, and like their European counterparts, “black Caribbean healers were in constant contact with the ideas of multifarious Atlantic origins, for oral and written traditions flowed through this region, which has defined its cosmopolitanism and transient population” (78). Far from depending on tradition or dogma, black Caribbean practitioners’ knowledge-creating strategies were based on experiential phenomena manufactured anew on the basis of localized circumstances and combining a vast arsenal of substances and ideas.

The three books + 1 draw on an array of sources in several languages and multiple archives. Inquisition records (Gómez), administrative protocols (Saraiva), and oral history and the press (Soto Laveaga) are used not only as testimonies of the complexity of history, but also as an evidence of the amount of work still to be done to display the itinerant character of knowledge.

I would like to close this review with a topic that often remains invisible: language, our most important tool. Gabriela Soto Laveaga grew up in the United States, of Mexican parents; the daughter of Héctor Soto Pérez, an immigrant who in 1971 became a professor of Chicano Studies at Cal State. This means that all three – Gómez, Saraiva, and Soto Laveaga – write and work in a linguistic context that is not the one in which they were born: behind these books, there is the effort involved in mastering a “foreign” universe. Perhaps this is one of the reasons why their work is always an invitation to confidently cross all kinds of borders, but always looking backwards, forwards, to the left, to the right, and with at least one reference book in the hand. An invitation that this review extends to the readership of *Tapuya*.

Additional information

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